

Quantum Spin as an Operator on a Physical State which Replaces Vector Operations? Part 3

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In two previous notes (Parts 1 and 2), we argued that spin matrices arise when one attempts to separate a quadratic equation (continuity equation with the Poynting vector for a photon, Klein-Gordon equation for a spin .5 particle) into two factors. These appear as generalized numbers (i.e. matrices) which may be multiplied together without considering vector operations such as the cross or dot product.

Here we try to examine the problem in an alternative way. We note first that in the case of the Klein-Gordon equation one has a 4-vector containing (p vector, E) or (r vector, t) to cite two examples. These transform under the unitary Lorentz transformation, i.e. via a unitary 4x4 matrix. A subset, however, namely p(x), p(y), p(z) or x,y,z of this 4-vector transforms physically under rotations in 3-space, i.e. via a 3x3 unitary matrix. Furthermore, there is an invariance under this 3x3 matrix transformation. In particular, objects such as the dot product or cross product do not change.

Classically, one has no issue with vector operators in an equation. In quantum mechanics, however, a free particle is described by the wavefunction $\exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r)$ and the operator $i \partial/\partial t$ and $-i \text{grad}$ return E and p (vector). $\exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r)$, however, describes a translational invariance in space and time, i.e. there is a periodicity. This invariance is clearly seen if the complex conjugate of the free particle wavefunction is multiplied by the wavefunction to yield 1 everywhere. Thus one starts with a quadratic equation W^*W and linearizes it to obtain the function $W(x,t)$. The operators which act on W are the generators related to the invariance in W^*W . For the quantum free particle, these are $i \partial/\partial t$ and $-i \text{grad}$. We suggest that if such a scheme exists for this translational invariance in t and r, one should treat the rotational invariance in the Klein-Gordon equation in a similar manner. In other words, there should exist operators and a function associated with rotational invariance. In this case, the operator is a matrix (Pauli matrices) and the function a spinor.

Dirac Equation

The Dirac equation arose after de Broglie suggested the existence of a wavelength for a particle with rest mass (e.g. electron) and Schrodinger wrote the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation: $-\frac{1}{2m} \text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} W(x,t) + V(x)W(x,t) = E W(x,t)$. A free particle solution is:

$$W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r) \quad ((1))$$

Issues arose as to the interpretation of such a solution as there does not exist a medium for a physical wave. Born thus described ((1)) as a probability wave. As a result, there exists a complex probability wave which has physical implications, i.e. it gives rise to n-slit interference-diffraction experimental results which do not follow from classical mechanics for a particle with rest mass. Operators $i \partial/\partial t$ and $-i \text{grad}$ are needed to extract E and p vector from this function.

Invariance Associated with $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$

We suggest that it is the translational invariance of $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ which is a key feature. First of all, one may see the periodicity of this function, meaning that it exists in all of space and time. This, we argue, suggests a kind of translational invariance in space and time. This may be seen more clearly by considering

$$W^*(x,t)W(x,t) = 1 \quad ((2))$$

1 is a constant for all space-time. We argue that there seems to be a recipe consisting of a quadratic expression of a function which describes a physical invariance. There also exist operators, generators of the invariance, which may extract physically observable information from this function. In particular, $\partial/\partial t$ and $-i \mathbf{grad}$ contain the generators d/dt and \mathbf{grad} for translations in time and space which are directly linked to translational invariance in these dimensions.

If this idea is true, then one should extend it to symmetries other than translational invariance.

The Klein-Gordon Equation

The Klein-Gordon equation is associated with a Lorentz invariant in 4-space i.e. Einstein's:

$$-\partial_\mu \partial^\mu \phi = -m^2 \phi \quad (c=1) \quad ((3))$$

One may, however, note that there exists a 3x3 rotational invariance contained in $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$. If such an invariance exists, then according to the recipe above, one should seek a function which linearizes $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$ as well as an operator associated with it. In the above section, it was noted that the invariance is most clearly displayed by a quadratic form. There we used:

$$W^*(x,t) W(x,t) = 1 \quad \text{where } W(x,t) \text{ is the free particle wavefunction} \quad ((4))$$

((3)) is already in a quadratic form, so one should seek a square root form to be consistent with $W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt+ i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$. In other words, one should linearize ((3)) as Dirac did. In his case, he used 4x4 matrices consisting of Pauli 2x2 matrices, Here we focus on the 2x2 Pauli matrices for simplicity. The goal is to have a linear equation which contains operators associated with the invariance in question as well as a function demonstrating the invariance. In the $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ case, $\partial/\partial t$ and $-i \mathbf{grad}$ represent translational operators which describe, mathematically, small translations in space, associated with translational invariance.

For rotational invariance, one expects to have a generator of rotations, which suggests a matrix. One might at first think that a 3x3 matrix is needed, but if one writes:

$$p(x) S_x + p(y) S_y + p(z) S_z \quad ((5))$$

and wishes this, multiplied by its complex conjugate, to yield $p \cdot p$ then:

$$S_x S_x = S_y S_y = S_z S_z = 1 \text{ and } S_x S_y + S_y S_x = S_x S_z + S_z S_x = S_y S_z + S_z S_y = 0 \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is satisfied by 2x2 Pauli matrices. These represent operators associated with rotational invariance and act on 2-vectors called spinors. For S_x , the eigenvectors (1,0), and (0,1) suggest rotation in one direction or the other. Even if one has rotation in one direction about the z axis, there is still unknown rotation about x and y. Thus, spin seems to be complicated.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics is associated with invariances. A free particle represents translational invariance through $\exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r) = W(x,t)$. This invariance is more clearly seen in the quadratic form, i.e. $W^*(x,t) W(x,t) = 1$. Thus one starts with a quadratic form displaying invariance and takes the square root (linearizes) to find a function which is associated with the invariance. There then exist operators which act on this function to yield physical observables. For translational invariance one has $\partial/\partial t$ and $-i \text{ grad}$ which yield E and p vector. These are also generators associated with the invariance in question, i.e. translational invariance.

In the case of the Klein-Gordon equation, based on $-E^2 + p \cdot p = -m^2$ ($c=1$), there exists rotational invariance in $p \cdot p$. According to the above recipe, one should linearize this equation to obtain operators associated with rotation and a rotational function. We use: $S_x p(x) + S_y p(y) + S_z p(z)$ and argue that when multiplied by its complex conjugate one should obtain $p \cdot p$. This yields the 2x2 Pauli matrices as a solution. They are thus generators of a kind of rotation, just as $\partial/\partial t$ and $-i \text{ grad}$ are generators of translation in x, r . The Pauli matrices act on a 2-vector (called a spinor). In the case of S_z , one has the eigenvectors (1,0) and (0,1) which suggest rotation in either one direction or the other.